

Teachers' Awareness of E-Based Educational Resource with Respect To Gender, Locality and Type of Management

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to find out teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources. 100 teachers (50 male and 50 female) from 20 higher education institutions of Pilibhit District, affiliated to Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, were selected randomly by employing stratified random sampling technique. A self-constructed questionnaire was used for collecting data. Survey method was used for present investigation and analyzed with p-value, Mean, SD and t-test and statistics. Findings of the study revealed that there was significant difference in awareness of urban and rural teachers. Urban teachers were significantly more aware about e-based educational resources as compared to rural teachers. Similarly, Teachers of private institutions were significantly more in their awareness about e-based educational resources as compared to government/aided teachers. Gender showed no significance difference in awareness of teachers about e-based educational resources.

Keywords: Awareness, E-Based Educational Resources, Teacher, Gender etc.

Introduction

Advancement of Information and Technology brought a boom in e-based educational resources which caused a great change in teaching-learning field and paved a path for digital learning, generally, known as e-learning. E-based educational resources paved a path for digital learning and it can be best seen during time of Covid-19 when country wide lockdown was prevailed and it became difficult to provide education. But these were e-based educational resources which facilitated education via-online mode. Emergence of e-based educational resources in the field of education has brought a great change in every aspect of education whether it is teaching, administration or evaluation. In every field, these resources helped education stakeholders. These resources gave a pace in education scenario by employing e-books, e-journal, e-library and other e-based educational resources to obtain learning material. It has become a need of present time to know and how to use e-based educational resources in teaching-learning process. **Krnchakkanvar (2014)** defined e-based educational resources or electronic resources are defined as resources which requires computer access or any other electronic product that delivers a collection of data in form of text, electronic journals, image collections, other multimedia products and numerical or graphical data etc. Similarly, **Karbozoba et al. (2018)** also defined e-based educational resources or electronic educational resources are the resources which are in digital form including structure, educational subject content, metadata about them, as well as, data, information, software necessary for its use in the educational process. In this digital world, where new methods of teaching are going on evolving such as multimedia method, how a teacher with old teaching method can exist in current teaching-learning scenario. They should be skilled in operating e-based educational resources to cope with the needs of the current education system. But being skilled in anything, first awareness is a pre-requisite for the same.

Awareness is the state of knowledge concerning something that exists or understanding of a state of affairs or subject at the current time based on information or expertise. (Ani & Ahiauzu). Generally, awareness about e-based educational resources means to being a state of consciousness or knowing about them. It is a skill to know and use them in teaching-learning perspectives.

Objectives

1. To find out gender wise difference of Teachers' Awareness of E-Based Educational Resources.
2. To find out Locality wise difference of Teachers' Awareness of E-Based Educational Resources.
3. To find out Type of Management wise difference of Teachers' Awareness of E-Based Educational Resources.

Hypotheses

- H1** There is significant difference between male and female teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.
- H2** There is significant difference between urban and rural teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.
- H3** There is significant difference between private and government/aided teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

Method

Survey Method was employed for the current study.

Population

Population of the present study consisted all the teachers, teaching in Higher Education Institutions of District Pilibhit, affiliated to Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

Sample and Sampling

Stratified Random Sampling was employed to select teachers as a sample. Sample consisted of 100 teachers (50 male and 50 female) from the population.

Tool

Teachers' E-based Educational Resources Test' was used to collect data.

Statistics

SD, Mean, t-test and p-value was used in treating and analysing the raw data.

Data Processing

The raw data was processed with (SPSS) version 22.0.

Levels of Significance

Hypotheses were tested at .05 level of Significance.

Analysis of Data

- H1** There is significant difference between male and female teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.
- H1** There is no significant difference between male and female teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

Table-1

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Male	50	18.9000	2.90847	1.272	.207	NS
Female	50	18.1200	3.21755			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .207 for awareness of e-based educational resources scores of Male and Female teachers working in higher education colleges. Here, p value is higher ($p > .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative

hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between Male and Female teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

H2 There is significant difference between urban and rural teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

H2 There is no significant difference between urban and rural teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

Table-2

Locality	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Urban	50	101.2200	13.17897	3.932	.000	S
Rural	50	90.7000	19.26957			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .000for awareness of e-based educational resources scores of Urban and Rural teachers working in Higher Education colleges. Here, p value is less ($p < .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is significant difference between urban and rural teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources. Urban teachers were significantly more in their awareness than those of rural.

H3 There is significant difference between private and government/aided teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

H3 There is no significant difference between private and government/aided teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources.

Table-3

Management	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Government/ Aided	50	16.7400	2.67116	7.016	.000	S
Private	50	20.2800	2.36505			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .000for awareness of e-based educational resources scores of Government/Aided and Private Teachers working in Higher Education colleges. Here, p value is less ($p < .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is significant difference between government / aided and private teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources. Private teachers were significantly more in their awareness of e-based educational resources as compared to government/aided teachers.

Graphical Representation of Analyzed Data

Findings

Findings of the study reveal that-

- Male and female teachers working in higher education institutions did not differ significantly with respect to awareness of E-based Educational Resources. It means there is no significant effect of Gender on Awareness of E-based Educational Resources.
- Urban and Rural teachers working in higher education institutions differed significantly with respect to Awareness of E-based Educational Resources. It means there is significant effect of Locality on Awareness of E-based Educational Resources.
- Government/Aided and Private teachers working in higher education institutions differed significantly with respect to Awareness of E-based Educational Resources. It means there is significant effect of Type of Management on Awareness of E-based Educational Resources.

Conclusion

The present study was conducted to find out teachers' awareness of E-based Educational Resources. Data was collected and analyzed with inferential statistics. Findings of the study revealed that Urban teachers and Private teachers were found more in their awareness than those of Rural teachers and Government/Aided teachers respectively. As far as effect of gender was concerned, the study did not find any significant effect of gender on teachers' awareness of e-based educational resources. Therefore, this study found no significant effect of gender on teachers' awareness. Teachers should be aware of e-based educational resources and should be competent in using them in teaching-learning process. Rural and government/aided teachers should be focused much for utilizing e-based educational resources because they were not as aware in using e-based educational resources in teaching-learning process as findings of this present investigation showed low awareness to e-based educational resources as compared to urban and private teachers.

Discussion

Awareness is a key-factor in proper implementation of e-based educational resources in current teaching-learning system. Covid-19 impacted every aspect of human life. How education can be remained uninfluenced from this phenomenon. Country wide lockdown during Covid-19 restricted the students physically for learning at schools and colleges. It affected their learning very much but e-based educational resources provided a hope of ray to facilitate teaching-learning during lockdown. Therefore, there is a need of proper implementation of e-based educational resources in teaching-learning process but for the same, teachers should be aware and know how to use these resources in teaching-learning process. Seminars, workshop, orientation programme etc. should be organised to spread knowledge and skill of using e-based educational resources in teaching-learning perspective to meet the objectives of current time education.

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